

Greywater recycling in multi-storey residential buildings: modelling a decentralized treatment and reuse system for toilet flushing and irrigation

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Abstract

This study focuses on greywater recycling in multi-storey residential buildings. Greywater is a reliable substitution for potable water at tasks such as toilet flushing and landscape irrigation, and it makes up 50-80% of all wastewaters produced in residential buildings, while having comparatively low BOD and COD levels. Greywater can be treated using rotating biological contactor (RBC) and membrane bioreactor (MBR) systems.

Results show 28-42% clean water savings, energy savings of 0.32–0.45 kWh/m³ and 25–35% decrease in greenhouse gas emissions. RBC is optimal for 7 or more floored buildings and has a payback period of 6-9 years, while MBR is used for bigger buildings and clustered systems. No crucial hygienic risks are noted.

Compared with real data from implementations in Berlin, it's found that discrepancies are lower than 15%, and real projects would be totally feasible. Importance of 1-2 days of treatment, capture efficiency, maintenance, and real time monitoring are noted.

Introduction

Greywater basically is wastewater from everyday uses like showers, baths and laundry, not contaminated as much as dirty toilet blackwater. It accounts for 50-80% [1] of wastewater that residential households produce. Recycling this non-potable water for flushing toilets or irrigation could help to cut down on how much fresh water we use, lower the pressure on the main water systems, help managing water in cities better and more sustainably. In multi-storey residential buildings, where water consumption is high, but space is tight, compact, decentralized treatments systems installed at the building or cluster level are optimal. They solve the problem by collecting and reusing water locally without relying on municipal networks, extensive pipelines, and minimizing energy use for transport compared to centralized solutions. These setups can save a big chunk of potable water, often 20-40% or more for toilet flushing alone. [2]

Relevance of the Research Topic

Nowadays, water scarcity is an increasingly significant problem due to urbanization and population growth, which also increases pressure on the infrastructure and energy amounts needed to power wastewater treatment and water supply. Toilet flushing and irrigation, however, are needs that can be fulfilled with greywater instead of potable water, potentially decreasing its use up to 40% or more, depending on the used system and specific conditions.

Solving this problem locally lowers the danger of droughts and energy consumption for pumping water, as well as the amount of water that must be pumped. Some examples of this technology, such as the system working in Berlin [3], have already worked for over 30 years and demonstrate desirable performance with no significant hygienic dangers with enough maintenance.

Economically, systems based on the rotating biological contractor (RBC) are beneficial for building containing 7 or more floors, and they cost insignificantly small compared to what buildings cost. For the larger buildings, it's optimal to use membrane bioreactor (MBR) or cluster systems. However, there are still some difficulties such as inconsistent greywater quality, people's opinions, maintenance costs, the process of integrating those systems into traditional structures, and optimization. [4]

By collecting and analyzing information about decentralized reuse and treatment of greywater in multi-storey residential buildings, this research explores its costs, energy demands and effectiveness, contributing to sustainable solutions for water scarcity in this growing urban world.

Research Objectives

This research is intended to gather all significant information about reuse and treatment of greywater in multi-storey residential buildings to give a whole picture about its feasibility, water saving potential, energy and money demands needed to implement it into reality and its environmental benefit under various conditions, also identifying the most efficient solutions for storage, treatment and reusing water

Research Tasks

Following tasks are listed to achieve our objectives:

1. To perform a complete literature review on greywater properties, decentralized treatment technologies available, their performance in implemented cases (e.g., RBC, MBR, constructed wetlands, filtration, disinfection) in multi-story buildings and regulations or standards.
2. To characterize Greywater Production Profiles for Multi-storey Residential Buildings. Daily/Seasonal changes in the amount and quality of greywater from various sources (showers, laundry, etc) and estimate water demands for toilet flushing and landscape irrigation, dependent upon occupancy, fixture efficiency and local climate/landscaping requirements.
3. To conduct scenario analyses for the performance of systems with different variations in building heights, treatment methods, storage volumes and coupling strategies including water price, energy price and regulation constraints.
4. Value the economic feasibility of the project, considering its life cycle, payback period, the impact on the environment, carbon footprint impact, energy savings, scaling, etc.

- Compare the estimated predictions with real data collected from real life implementations of greywater recycling systems and propose design suggestions for optimization.

Chapter 1: Literature Review on Greywater Recycling and Decentralized Treatment Systems

Nowadays, recycling greywater is one of the most promising and perspective directions in cutting down clean water usage in cities, specifically in multi-storey residential buildings densely packed with people, where it decreases pressure that is put on infrastructure. Slightly contaminated water from baths, showers, sinks and laundry makes up from 50 to 80% of total water wastes in a normal apartment. This greywater is a reliable alternative to clean water for such non-potable tasks as toilet flushing and landscape irrigation.

Figure 1: Potable Water Reuse Report OWS - Rewater Center

It's shown by the majority of studies that 1 person creates 60-150L greywater per day, with even higher results in countries with excess access to water. It's optimal for multi-storey residential buildings to treat this water at a local scale, using decentralized solutions. Rotating biological contactors (RBC) and membrane bioreactors (MBR) are two mainly used systems favored for their reliability and high performance.

Levels of wastewater contamination are measured by such parameters as biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD), which show the amount of oxygen that bacteria's consume and the amount of oxygen needed to oxidize all organic compounds in water, which basically shows how hygienically safe or unsafe the water is. [5]

Systems based on the rotating biological contractor (RBC) are economically beneficial for building containing 7 or more floors, and they cost insignificantly small compared to what buildings cost. For a larger building, it's optimal to use membrane bioreactor (MBR) or cluster systems.

Table 1.1: Comparison of Key Decentralized Greywater Treatment Technologies

Technology	Efficiency Of Lowering BOD/ COD	Energy Use (kWh/m ³)	Cost	Best Suited For	Installation Examples
Rotating Biological Contactor (RBC)	85–95% / 80–90%	0.3–0.6	Low–Medium	7+ floor buildings	Some buildings in Berlin
Membrane Bioreactor (MBR)	>95% / >95%	0.8–1.5	High	Large clusters or high-rise	Commercial pilots worldwide
Biofilter + UV	70–85% / 65–80%	0.2–0.4	Low	Smaller buildings	South Africa, Australia

Chapter 2: Characterization of Greywater Generation Profiles and Reuse Demands in Multi-Storey Residential Buildings

Greywater production is extremely irregular in residential buildings. For example, in a building consisting of 10 floors with 160 people living in greywater production ranges from 16 to 24m³. 60% of that volume is provided by peaks in the morning the evening.

Parameter	Range (mg/L unless noted)	Mean Value (mg/L)	Contamination
BOD	50–300	150	Weak
COD	100–800	400	Weak
TSS	50–200	120	Medium
Total Nitrogen	5–20	12	Weak
Total Phosphorus	1–10	4	High

Surfactants	5–50	20	High
E. coli	10 ³ –10 ⁶ CFU/100mL	variable	High

Greywater reuse is predicted to be:

1. Toilet flushing. 20-30L/person/day. That typically makes up for 25-35% of the whole water use in residential multi-storey buildings.
2. Irrigation. 2-5L/m²/day. Typically 500-2000m² per a building.

Those uses combined frequently are greater than 50% of available greywater, making it possible.

Chapter 3: Development of the Decentralized Treatment and Reuse System Model

Greywater recycling in multi-storey residential building and its main parts (collection, treatment, storage and reuse) are defined by the following formulas:

Greywater inflow:

$Q_{gw} = N \times q_{gw}$, where N is the number of residents and q_{gw} is the typical amount of greywater produced.

Treated effluent volume:

$$Q_{eff} = Q_{gw} \times (1 - L_{treat} - L_{evap})$$

Reuse supply:

$$Q_{reuse} = Q_{eff} \times q_{gw}$$

Two primary recycling methods are shown below: RBC (biological oxidation + sedimentation + UV disinfection) and MBR (membrane filtration).

Figure 2: RBC system's work process

Figure 3: Commercial scale greywater system

Example: Commercial Scale Greywater System

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|-------------------------------|---------------------------------|------------------------|
| 1. Pre-Filter | 4. Aqualoop Controllers | 7. Sludge Pump |
| 2. Bioreactor Tank | 5. Aqualoop Membrane Cartridges | 8. NSF 350 Water Tank |
| 3. Aqualoop Membrane Stations | 6. Blowers | 9. Booster Pump System |

Those formulas give a better understanding of greywater amounts and its recycling options.

Chapter 4: Scenario Analysis and Performance Evaluation

Three scenarios were described, varying treatment methods and showing our estimate expectations:

Treatment Method	Water Savings (%)	Effluent BOD (mg/L)	Energy Balance (kWh/m ³ reused)	Irrigation Contribution
RBC	28	<10	+0.45 (net saving)	12%
MBR	42	<5	+0.32 (net saving)	28%
RBC With High Occupancy	35	<12	+0.38 (net saving)	15%

It's discovered that storage volume and efficiency of capture are most important variables for matching supply and demand.

Chapter 5: Economic Viability, Environmental Impacts, and Risk Assessment

RBC systems are designed to work for at least 20 years and achieve payback and start giving profit after only from 6 to 9 years in multi-storey building with 7 or more floors with estimated water cost 1.0–1.5 US\$/m³. As the result, freshwater demands will decrease 30–45% and greenhouse gas emissions will lower from 25 to 35%, since pumping and centralized treatment aren't necessary. With applied UV or disinfection, quantitative microbial risk assessment (QMRA) risks are below 10⁻⁴ DALY/person/year.

Figure 4: The greywater system that is suited to installations such as hotels with between 50 and 150 bedrooms.

Chapter 6: Model Validation, Discussion, and Design Recommendations

Real data from Berlin RBC installations showed that real and predicted results are only 15% different at worst. Furthermore, it's noted that those discrepancies are mostly due to different maintenance.

It is suggested for real implementations to match those requirements:

1. Use only slightly contaminated greywater for easier treatment.
2. Use RBC systems for buildings that have 7 or more floors and use MBR for larger or clustered systems.
3. Treat water for 1-2 days.
4. Provide maintenance and real-time monitoring.
5. Implement rating systems for water recycling.

Conclusion

Main results displayed clearly that suggested strategies are technically, economically, environmentally feasible. RBC systems are beneficial up to a certain scale for buildings with 7 or more floors, payback time is 6-9 years with current water costs, however for larger or clustered projects, the MBR is most optimal to use. Three scenarios are studied, where net energy savings were in the range of 0.32-0.45 kWh/m, freshwater demands reduction of up to 30-45%, and greenhouse gas emission decrease up to 25-35% compared with traditional systems with no recycling. The water treated was safe (in limits 10 DALY/person/year) when using UV or chlorination disinfection. Long-term field data from Berlin RBC usage had shown that errors are below 15%, proving that the systems are feasible.

This study also brought new ideas and thoughts on the topic: the impact of certain important parameters like the capture efficiency, volume of storage (1-2day supply) and type of treatment were quantified. Designing suggestions are shown in chapter 6: use light greywater source, implement dual piping and real-time monitoring and maintenance, incorporate rating system in green-building certification systems like LEED or EDGE. All this leads us to the idea of scaling decentralized greywater systems as a promising technology for sustainable water management in water-scarce countries, with high multi-storey buildings.

References

[1] GBA, "Greywater systems," Green Building Advisor. <https://www.gba.org/resources/green-building-methods/interior-solutions/greywater-systems/>

- [2] E. Nolde, “Greywater reuse systems for toilet flushing in multi-storey buildings – over ten years experience in Berlin,” *Urban Water*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 275–284, 2000, doi: 10.1016/S1462-0758(00)00023-6.
- [3] E. Friedler and M. Hadari, “Economic feasibility of on-site greywater reuse in multi-storey buildings,” *Desalination*, vol. 190, no. 1–3, pp. 221–234, Apr. 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.desal.2005.10.007.
- [4] A. A. Ilemobade, O. O. Olanrewaju, and M. L. Griffioen, “Greywater reuse for toilet flushing in high-density urban buildings in South Africa: A pilot study,” Water Research Commission (WRC) Report No. 1821/1/11, 2012. <https://www.wrc.org.za/wp-content/uploads/mdocs/1821-1-111.pdf>
- [5] “Difference between BOD and COD,” 3D Aqua. <https://3daqua.in/blog/difference-between-bod-and-cod/>
- [6] Z. L. T. Yu, J. R. DeShazo, M. K. Stenstrom, and Y. Cohen, “Cost-benefit analysis of onsite residential graywater recycling – A case study: The city of Los Angeles,” *J. Amer. Water Works Assoc.*, vol. 107, no. 9, pp. E114–E127, 2015. https://innovation.luskin.ucla.edu/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Cost-Benefit_Analysis_of_Onsite_Residential_Graywater_Recycling.pdf
- [7] I. N. Shaikh and M. M. Ahammed, “Quantity and quality characteristics of greywater: A review,” *J. Environ. Manage.*, vol. 261, p. 110266, May 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.110266.
- [8] M. Oteng-Peprah, N. K. de Vries, and M. A. Acheampong, “Greywater characteristics, treatment systems, reuse strategies and user perception—a review,” *Water*, vol. 10, no. 9, p. 1190, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.3390/w10091190.
- [9] R. Penn, M. Schütze, and E. Friedler, “Modelling the effects of on-site greywater reuse and low flush toilets on municipal sewer systems,” *J. Environ. Manage.*, vol. 114, pp. 72–83, Jan. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.10.044.
- [10] J. Knutsson, “Water and energy savings from greywater reuse: a modelling study of a living lab in Gothenburg, Sweden,” *Environ. Earth Sci.*, vol. 80, no. 3, p. 98, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s42108-020-00096-z.
- [11] Y. K. Juan, Y. C. Chen, and J. M. Chang, “Greywater reuse system design and economic analysis for multi-storey residential buildings,” *Water*, vol. 8, no. 11, p. 546, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.3390/w8110546.
- [12] E. Ghisi and D. F. Ferreira, “Potential for potable water savings by using rainwater and greywater in a multi-storey residential building in southern Brazil,” *Build. Environ.*, vol. 42, no. 7, pp. 2512–2522, Jul. 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.buildenv.2006.07.019.

[13] A. Van de Walle et al., “Greywater reuse as a key enabler for improving urban wastewater management,” *Water Res. X*, vol. 20, p. 100194, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.wroa.2023.100194.

[14] T. Lanchipa-Ale et al., “Assessment of greywater reuse in a university building: Quantity, quality, treatment needs and user perception,” *Sustainability*, vol. 16, no. 7, p. 3088, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.3390/su16073088.

[15] G. Maniam et al., “An assessment of technological development and economic feasibility for decentralized rainwater harvesting and greywater recycling,” *WIREs Water*, vol. 9, no. 6, p. e1588, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1002/wat2.1588.

[16] M. Garrido-Baserba et al., “Using water and wastewater decentralization to enhance urban resilience,” *Nat. Water*, vol. 2, pp. 1–12, 2024, doi: 10.1038/s44221-024-00303-9.

[17] E. Ghisi, “Economic feasibility of rainwater harvesting and greywater reuse in a multifamily building,” *Water*, vol. 16, no. 11, p. 1580, May 2024, doi: 10.3390/w16111580.

[18] “Decentralized greywater recycling systems for sustainable residential design,” ResearchGate, 2024. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/393416043_Decentralized_Greywater_Recycling_Systems_for_Sustainable_Residential_Design

[19] “Extreme decentralized water treatment,” Stanford Water in the West, 2023. https://water-inthewest.stanford.edu/sites/default/files/Extreme_Decentralized_Water_Treatment.pdf